

COMBINED ASCORBIC ACID IN PLANT FOODSTUFFS. PART II.

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Further evidence has been presented to show the presence of combined ascorbic acid in cabbage. It has been extracted from dried cabbage and biological evidence has been given to show that the substance extracted is combined ascorbic acid.

In the preceding paper (Pal and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1939, **16**, 481) evidence has been given to show that in several plant tissues part of the ascorbic acid is present in the combined state. In the present work we have attempted to find a solvent which would be most effective for the extraction of ascorbigen from dried cabbage. Chloroform seems to be the best solvent for this purpose, though it does not extract ascorbigen completely (Tables I—IV). It does not extract free ascorbic acid.

The action of hydrogen sulphide on this chloroform extract was investigated both in the hot and cold conditions. It was observed that by cold H_2S treatment no dye-reducing substance was produced, showing that no dehydroascorbic acid was present in the chloroform extract. This should dispose of the point of Mack and Tressler (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, **118**, 740) that the increase in reducing value on heating plant tissues may be due to the production of reducing substances from dehydroascorbic acid. In the present experiments the chloroform extract did not produce any reducing substance by cold treatment with H_2S , showing the absence of dehydroascorbic acid in the extract, while in the hot condition the effects of H_2S and N_2 were similar (Tables V and VI).

Chloroform extracts of ascorbigen can be concentrated considerably simply by extraction with water, which extracts ascorbigen completely while it dissolves only about 20% of the total solids of the chloroform extract.

The nature of the reducing substance or substances formed by heating the chloroform extracts in nitrogen was tested by the action of ascorbic acid oxidase. The reducing substances (64.8-70.6%) disappeared on treatment with the oxidase (prepared from cucumber), which, while it indicated that the bulk of the reducing substances formed by heat was ascorbic acid, also showed the presence of non-specific reducing substances in the combined state in cabbage extracts.

Finally, in order to test whether the chloroform extract of cabbage contained combined ascorbic acid, biological experiments were carried out with these extracts. The curative technique was adopted with guinea-pigs and it was found that the effects of feeding ascorbigen in the form of the chloroform extract and equivalent quantities of ascorbic acid were comparable (Figs. 1-3).

Preliminary results of this work have been published elsewhere (Guha and Sen-Gupta, *Science and Culture*, 1937, 3, 49; Guha and Sen-Gupta, *Nature*, 1938, 141, 974).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction by Different Solvents.

In each of the following experiments, 10 g. of green cabbage were taken, ground with sand and dried completely at 40° in an oven. The ascorbigen of the dried cabbage was extracted with different solvents, the solvents evaporated off by means of an electric fan, the residue treated with water and heated on a water-bath for 10 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen and the reducing substances formed were estimated by titrating with 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. All ascorbigen values are given in terms of the ascorbic acid that is produced on heating the ascorbigen preparations in water in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of cabbage (Tables I—IV).

TABLE I.

Extraction with ether and benzene.

	1st Expt.	2nd Expt.	3rd Expt.
Free ascorbic acid in green cabbage	0.306 mg.	0.320 mg.	0.312 mg.
Free ascorbic acid in dried cabbage	0.104	0.117	0.113
Ascorbigen extracted with ether (in terms of ascorbic acid)	0.0106	0.0212	0.0213
Ascorbigen extracted with benzene (in terms of ascorbic acid)	0.0127	0.0274	0.0335
Free ascorbic acid in aqueous extract of the evaporated benzene extract	0	0	0
Do ether extract	0	0	0

TABLE II.

Extraction with benzene and acetone.

	1st Expt.	2nd Expt.	3rd Expt.
Free ascorbic acid in green cabbage	0.266 mg.	0.257 mg.	0.265 mg.
Free ascorbic acid in dried cabbage	0.103	0.104	0.104
Ascorbigen extracted with benzene	0.0196	0.0196	0.0193
Ascorbigen extracted with acetone	0.015	0.014	0.015
Free ascorbic acid in the aqueous extract of the evapo- rated benzene extract	0	0	0
Do acetone extract	0	0	0

TABLE III.

Extraction with benzene and chloroform.

	1st Expt.	2nd Expt.	3rd Expt.
Free ascorbic acid in green cabbage	0.266 mg.	0.285 mg.	0.281 mg.
Free ascorbic acid in dried cabbage	0.114	0.113	0.107
Ascorbigen extracted with benzene	0.0189	0.0179	0.018
Ascorbigen extracted with chloroform	0.0266	0.0241	0.0273
Free ascorbic acid in the aqueous extract of the evaporated benzene extract	0	0	0
Do chloroform extract	0	0	0

TABLE IV.

Extraction with chloroform and petroleum ether (b. p. 40°).

	1st Expt.	2nd Expt.
Free ascorbic acid in green cabbage	0.281 mg.	0.277 mg.
Free ascorbic acid in dried cabbage	0.0912	0.0896
Ascorbigen extracted with chloroform	0.0203	0.0231
Ascorbigen extracted with petroleum ether (b p. 40°)	0.0179	0.0173
Free ascorbic acid in aqueous extract of the evaporated		
(1) Chloroform extract	0	0
(2) Petroleum ether extract	0	0

Action of Sulphuretted Hydrogen.

(a) In each of the following sets of experiments 15 g. of dried cabbage were taken and ascorbigen extracted with chloroform. After evaporation of the solvent the residue was treated with water and diluted to 50 c.c. This was divided into two equal portions, one of which was heated for 15 minutes in sulphuretted hydrogen and the other in nitrogen.

TABLE V.

	Ascorbic acid value after heating in	
	H ₂ S.	N ₂ .
1st Expt.	0.293 mg.	0.300 mg.
2nd Expt.	0.431	0.431
3rd Expt.	0.353	0.358

(b) In each of the following sets of experiments, 20 g. of dried cabbage were taken and ascorbigen was extracted with chloroform. The solvent was evaporated off and the residue was treated with water and diluted to 50 c.c. This was divided into four equal portions, which were treated variously (Table VI).

TABLE VI.

	Ordinary titration without heating.	After heating in N ₂ .	After heating in H ₂ S.	After treatment with H ₂ S in the cold.
1st Expt.	0 mg.	0.0542 mg.	0.0542 mg.	0 mg.
2nd Expt.	0	0.071	0.071	0

Concentration of Ascorbigen.

The dried cabbage (15 g.) was treated with chloroform at 40° for 2 hours with intermittent shaking. The chloroform extract was taken in a weighed glass basin and evaporated and kept in a vacuum desiccator overnight and then the basin with its contents reweighed. In two experiments, the weights of the residues were 0.1782 g. and 0.2244 g. respectively. On extracting these residues with 15 c.c. of water, only 0.0300 g. and 0.0304 g. respectively came out in the aqueous solution, *i.e.*, only about 20% and 12% respectively of the chloroform-soluble solids were extracted with water and the aqueous fractions contained practically all the ascorbigen which amounted to 0.13 mg. in terms of ascorbic acid in each case.

Action of Ascorbic Acid Oxidase on Concentrated Chloroform Extracts.

The chloroform extract of 10 g. of dried cabbage was evaporated and treated with water. This was centrifuged and the centrifugate diluted to 30 c.c. after heating in an atmosphere of N₂.

TABLE VII.

	A s c o r b i c A c i d				
	1st. Expt.	2nd. Expt.	3rd. Expt.	4th Expt.	5th. Expt.
(1) Ordinary titration (10 c.c.)	0.0346 mg.	0.0416 mg.	0.0378 mg.	0.0346 mg.	0.0378 mg.
(2) 10 C.c. of this solution + 3 c.c. of acetate buffer (p _H 5.6) + 2 c.c. water at 40° for ½ hour.	0.0346	0.0416	0.0378	0.0346	0.0378
(3) 10 c.c. of solution + 3 c.c. of acetate buffer (p _H 5.6) + 2 c.c. oxidase solution at 40° for ½ hour.	0.011	0.0118	0.0120	0.0123	0.0132
(4) Percentage of oxidation of the heat-produced reducing substances by oxidase.	68.5	70.6	66.0	64.8	65.0

Control experiments were carried out with (1) 10 c.c. of ascorbic acid solution containing the same amount of ascorbic acid as was obtained in the above experiments + 3 c.c. of acetate buffer (p_H 5.6) + 2 c.c. of oxidase solution at 40° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and (2) the same mixture in which 10 c.c. of ascorbic acid solution were replaced by 10 c.c. of water. No values for ascorbic acid were obtained in these experiments.

Biological Experiments with Ascorbigen.

Biological experiments were carried out with male guinea-pigs weighing between 190 and 250 g. Their diet consisted of powdered gram (20 parts), powdered oats (80 parts), and salt mixture (1 part) and each animal was given daily 25 c.c. of milk, autoclaved for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 10 lb. pressure. The animals were divided into 5 groups. The first group was given scorbutic diet alone. They developed typical signs of scurvy and died (Fig. 1). The second group of animals received 2 mg. of synthetic *l*-ascorbic

FIG. 1.

Animals on a scorbutic diet.

acid daily as a supplement to the scorbutic diet after their weight began to fall (Fig 2). The third group of animals had a similar supplement with 2 mg. of an ascorbigen preparation (chloroform extract) equivalent in reducing substances as measured by titration with the indophenol indicator to 2 mg. of ascorbic acid. As true ascorbic acid was in fact only about 60-70%

FIG. 2.

Scorbutic diet supplemented with

† ascorbigen preparation equiv. to 2 mg. of reducing substance,

‡ 2 mg. of ascorbic acid.

of the total reducing substances, this dose gave slightly less than 2 mg. of ascorbic acid equivalent. The curves for these animals are given in Fig. 2. for comparison. The fourth group of animals received 4 mg. or 5 mg. of synthetic *l*-ascorbic acid and the fifth group received equivalent amounts of reducing substances present in the ascorbigen preparation obtained from dried cabbage (Fig. 3). It will be observed that the curves for groups of animals on comparable doses of ascorbigen and ascorbic acid are comparable, although those animals which were receiving ascorbigen were actually receiving slightly less ascorbic acid than the animals on pure ascorbic acid supplement.

FIG. 3.

Scorbic diet supplemented with

ϕ — ascorbigen preparation equiv. to 5 mg. of reducing substance,

x — " " " " 4 " " "

ψ — 5 mg. of ascorbic acid.

$\uparrow$ — 4 mg. of " "

DISCUSSION.

It has been shown that chloroform can extract ascorbigen from dried cabbage to a certain extent. This extract does not decolorise the indophenol

indicator, showing the absence of free ascorbic acid. But when heated in nitrogen it gives a dye-reducing value, about 60-70% of which disappears on treatment with ascorbic acid oxidase. This shows that the bulk of the reducing substances is probably ascorbic acid. While, therefore, there is ascorbigen present in the chloroform extracts, these experiments indicate the presence of other non-specific reducing substances in a combined state.

The reducing substances formed by heating the chloroform extract cannot be degradation products of dehydroascorbic acid as suggested by Mack and Tressler (*loc. cit.*), as the chloroform extract does not give any dye-reducing value on treatment with sulphuretted hydrogen in the cold and therefore does not contain any dehydroascorbic acid.

Biological experiments show that the chloroform extracts are active and their activity is comparable with that of roughly equivalent quantities of pure ascorbic acid. It should be noted that in these biological experiments the ascorbigen preparation contained about 30% less ascorbic acid than the reduction value would indicate, as about 30% consists of non-specific reducing substances. The performance of the animals on ascorbigen was nevertheless comparable with that of animals on pure ascorbic acid.

It has been shown that considerable concentration of ascorbigen can be effected by evaporating the solvent from the chloroform extract of cabbage and then extracting with water. This process extracts all the ascorbigen of the chloroform extract but only about 20% of the total solids. Chloroform, however, does not extract ascorbigen completely from dried cabbage and in subsequent work we have adopted other methods for concentration of ascorbigen.

C O N C L U S I O N .

Chloroform has been found to be the most effective solvent for the extraction of ascorbigen from dried cabbage. The chloroform extract does not reduce the indophenol indicator in the cold and is, therefore, free from ascorbic acid. Treatment with sulphuretted hydrogen in the cold does not produce any dye-reducing value, showing the absence of dehydroascorbic acid, but when heated in an atmosphere of hydrogen sulphide or nitrogen, dye-reducing substances are produced in equal quantities.

About 60-70% of the reducing substances produced by heat disappear on ascorbic acid oxidase treatment, from which it appears that, apart

from ascorbigen, cabbage contains some non-specific reducing substances in a combined state. Biological tests with guinea-pigs by the curative method, in which equivalent quantities of an ascorbigen preparation (chloroform extract of cabbage) and pure ascorbic acid were fed, give comparable results.

By extracting dried cabbage with chloroform, evaporating the solvent and extracting with water, some concentration of the ascorbigen can be effected.

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